

A Feminist Stylistic Analysis of Umm-e-Rumman Syed's Selected Poems in *Beautiful Inadequacies*

ABSTRACT:

This research attempts to analyze Umm-e-Rumman Syed's Poetry collection from a feminist stylistic perspective to investigate various stylistic elements used for male and female characters. This anthology of poetry book *Beautiful Inadequacies* is written by an emerging Pakistani poetess, Umm-e-Rumman Syed, and was published in August 2020. This collection of poetry is divided into two parts, "Reminiscence of Adolescence" and "Reminiscence of Adolescence and Beyond," which portray life from age 13 to 17 and from 17 to 20, respectively, in a total of 130 poems (35-95). The present study aims to examine the cruel and unjust attitude of society toward women. The study employs Sara Mills's Feminist Stylistic theory (1995) to examine how women are presented in a text. This study uses textual analysis as a methodology to examine words, phrases/sentences, discourses, and themes of different selected poems from the proposed text. Moreover, the writer has used generic nouns, women as the marked form, endearment and diminutives at the level of the word, metaphors, transitivity choices, presupposition and inferences at the level of phrase/sentence, and fragmentation at the discourse level. The study concluded that different terms are used for women, which shows the lower, passive, dependent nature of women in society and also shows some hope, bravery, resistance, and self-realization. Meanwhile, men are shown as active actors in all their actions.

KEY WORDS:

Beautiful Inadequacies, Umm-e-Rumman Syed, Reminiscence of Adolescence, Feminism, Stylistics, Self-realization

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Introduction

The dominant discourse reveals that sexist language is widely used by females. Music, film, drama, and media negatively propagate them. Female writers are influenced by male writers in literature. However, Umm-e-Rumman Syed uses different feminist stylistic elements for males and females in her poetry to reveal the negative nature of males and the subordinated position of females. This research attempts to analyze Umm-e-Rumman Syed's Poetry collection from a feminist stylistic perspective to investigate various stylistic elements used for male and female characters. This anthology of poetry book *Beautiful Inadequacies* is written by an emerging Pakistani poetess,, Umm-e-Rumman Syed,, and was published in August 2020. This collection of poetry is divided into two parts, "Reminiscence of Adolescence" and "Reminiscence of Adolescence and Beyond," which portray life from age 13

to 17 and from 17 to 20, respectively, in a total of 130 poems (35-95). The present study aims to examine the cruel and unjust attitude of society toward women. The study employs Sara Mills's Feminist Stylistic theory (1995) to examine how women are presented in a text. This study uses textual analysis as a methodology to examine words, phrases/sentences, discourses, and themes of different selected poems from the proposed text (McKee, 2003). Moreover, the writer has used generic nouns, women as the marked form, endearment and diminutives at the level of the word, metaphors, transitivity choices, presupposition and inferences at the level of phrase/sentence, and fragmentation at the discourse level. The study concluded that different terms are used for women that show the lower, passive, dependent nature of women in society and also show some hope, bravery, resistance, and self-realization, whereas men are shown as active actors in all the actions.

Literature Review

Shah et al. (2014), in their research *representation of women in Mann O Salwa: A Case Study through Feminist Stylistic Analysis*, attempt to answer the question of whether Pakistani female writers succeed in presenting a positive image of women through their use of linguistic choices or presented them weak, passive, distorted, and dependent on man. The researchers aim to explore whether the writing of Pakistani female authors is socially influenced by males and whether the character is subordinated to men. They also introduce those actions that lead to the suppression of women.

Kang & Xianyou (2015), in their research *Transitivity System and Thematic Meaning: A Feminist Stylistic Approach to Lawrence Is Lady Chatterley Lover*, explore the theme of male dominance through transitivity choices in the selected work. The study aims to identify that male action is different from female action and what those specific actions are that make males dominant over females. The study adopts Sara Mills's (1995) theory of feminist stylistic analysis at phrase/sentence level and transitivity choices to examine to what extent female characters are the target of circumstance and male characters are free of making their own decision and carrying out an action. The notion of transitivity is associated with Michael Halliday, who asserts that transitivity is a set of choices where the speaker deliberately encodes his internal and external experiences of the world and adjusts with the participant in those processes and their associated circumstances.

Darwesh and Hussain (2016), in their research *investigating a Feminist tendency in Margret Atwood's "The Handmaid's Tale"* in terms of the Sara Mills Model, a Feminist stylistic study, examine a relationship between socially fabricated meaning and structural element of linguistics in the selected text. The researchers aim to examine the lexical items in the novel, which seems to be doubtful of what actually takes place. The researchers adopt Sara Mills's (1995) feminist Stylistic theory at word, phrase/sentence, and discourse level to unfold the ideology, sexism, and sociocultural standards in *The Handmaid's Tale*.

Theoretical Framework

The researcher adopted Sara Mill's Framework of Feminist stylistics (1995) as a theoretical framework for the study. This Model contains three levels: word, phrase/sentence, and discourse level. In this study, the researcher will look for generic nouns, women as the marked form, endearments and diminutive at a word level, metaphor, transitivity choice, presupposition and inferences at phrase/sentence level, and fragmentation at discourse level. The purpose of the Feminist stylistic framework is to portray the message in linguistic structure in such a way that not only includes gender issues but also uses stylistics in a new way. This model not only looks for sexist words used in a text but also includes other things like metaphors, focalization, character, etc. (p. 13).

Sexist Language

The language obtains an unfair representation toward a person or gender, especially to females but sometimes to men also. The language is called sexist when it excludes either males or females when discussing a topic about both genders.

Effects of the Sexist Language Use

Sexist language may isolate female interrogators and cause them to feel they are not discussed. Sexist language may be one of the aspects that cause women to look at themselves in an unfavorable mood. It also brings confusion among both male and female genders as to whether language is used as a generic noun or pronoun or as a gender-specific one. (Mills's, [1995](#), p. 72)

Stylistic

The word stylistic came from "style," which is defined "as a systematic variation of a language" (Enkvist, 1973, p. 4). (Mills's, [1995](#)) defines Stylistic as a process of textual interpretation in which primacy of space is given to language (P, 3). This means that language plays a vital role in stylistics because the different forms and patterns that develop linguistic structure have important functions in the interpretation of a text. Stylistic focus on "what to say" and "how to say it" since the same context may be expressed in different linguistic forms. Mills ([1995](#)) asserts that stylistics is interested in the function of text in context (P, 6). It means that it acknowledges that the utterance is produced in a particular time, place, and culture.

Feminist Stylistics

The term feminist stylistic is the combination of feminism and stylistic which means the model of femmodel that acquires the linguistic interpretation of a text in a new style Mills ([1995](#)). Feminist stylistics deals with gender issues that were defined by Mills ([1995](#)). She stated that gender refers to diversity between men and women; both have different issues, but the man problem was brought to the surface, and that of a woman was ignored. (P, 13)

Word Level

Generic Noun

A noun that is used to point out the entire class of person, place, or thing. Because of the sexist language, all generic nouns portray male experiences of the world as standard or norm. For example, the book title "Prehistoric Man" seems to be used generically, but it is used only for the male representative of the breed whose adventure is eventually explained in depth, while women's action is only depicted as secondary. Mills stated that man is used as a prefix, such as a manhour, or an affix, such as seaman or fisherman because there is no generic alternative to such a noun. Generic nouns are not limited to 'man'; there are also some nouns and verbs that are used in the same way. Some words are specific for males but also refer to women as well. (67-69)

Generic Pronoun

It is also called a common gender pronoun, or gender-neutral pronoun. Mills defines the Generic pronoun as a noun that is used for both masculine and feminine items but is usually used in a discriminative way to allude to the people operating in a stereotypical male and female occupation. For example, the pronoun "he" is usually a determined male figure such as, when person A says I am going to complain to the director and person B replies do you think he will listen to you. Here in the later sentence speaker B assumed that all the directors should be male. (Mills, [1995](#), p. 66).

Women as the Marked Form

Markedness is a condition in which one linguistic component is more clearly described (marked) than the other (unmarked). In the English language woman is always seen as marked while a man is unmarked it means that a man and the work undertaken by a man are considered to be standard or norm whereas women and their work are considered to be diverged from the standard. For example, Male: Poet, Steward, author, host, while Female: Poetess, Stewardess, authoress, hostess. Mills explains that marked terms like Poetess and actress are used for Females to

show their lack of seriousness. Moreover, Mills asserts that marked form also refers to females showing their deviation from males (Mills, [1995](#), pp. 70-71).

Gender Free Language

The language that abstains the unfair representation towards an individual person or gender. (CERTAIN CHOICES). All the address terms should be used as truly generic until and unless gender-specific term is required. Use the plural pronoun. For example, when the authors have completed their literary work, they will mail them to the publisher. Use S/He, for example; when the author has completed his/her literary work, she will mail it to the publisher. Using alternative pronouns means sometimes using "She" for the first-person appearance of the pronoun rather than "he" (Mills, [1995](#), p. 72,73).

The Semantic Derogation of Women

It is the deflation of women-associated terms through the addition of abrogating sensual meaning. It means that there are certain gender-specific words for both males and females where the semantic or grammatical rules for male words are positive, while for females, the meaning is negative. For example Male; courtier, Sir, Bachelor, while female; courtesan, madam, spinster. Such as the male term courtier means someone who works in a court or who is linked to court while the female term courtesan means intimate servant or a hooker (Mills, [1995](#), p. 83,84).

Naming and Androcentrism

Androcentrism is the combination of two Greek words, Andro, which means strong and forceful, while centric is a Greek word originating from the Latin word "Kentrikos," which means to relate to center. Androcentrism is a sociological word that shows the liability of using a male point of view in a natural description of the world. That's why some feminists claim that women have to see their experiences through a male point of view and they, by themselves, don't create a new meaning. For example, for male sexual organs, they use joking names like dick, cock, and prick, while for female sexual organs, they use the word vagina, which is derived from the Latin word that means "Sheath," a place to keep a sword, but when women give birth to a child the name of this part change into the birth canal (Mills, [1995](#), p. 78,79).

Endearments and Diminutive

A word that is understood as conveying minuteness and endearment. There is a list of words that someone uses for their wife or fellow female partner as affection, but these terms can also mean disgrace or shame. For example, my chick, my honey, my doll, my sugar, all these sentences are used for women, and it shows that woman is some delicious food to eat. Mills stated that diminutives can be used to show affection, but they can also be used to demean someone; males use this term to maintain hierarchical relationships (Mills, [1995](#), p. 89).

Taboo and Euphemism

Euphemism means to say something in a good way or to use nice and polite words to replace unpleasant and taboo words. There are some usual experiences in women's life that they cannot mention publicly and they are considered taboo. So, there are euphemistic terms used for these things such as, the word menstruation is considered a taboo word so they use the euphemistic term "periods" for it which indicates a duration of time rather than blood flow (Mill, [1995](#), p. 90).

Phrase / Sentence Leve

Readymade Phrases

Readymade phrases are those pieces of writing that have been placed in a passage by someone else. Some certain phrases/sentences are pre-constructed in a sexist way which seems to present women in a bad way. For example,

the way to a man's heart is through his stomach. This shows that for a happy and pleasant life, women must have a relationship with a man, and to establish this relationship, women must do some work to attract men's hearts, like cooking. Readymade phrases are used to degrade women and present them in a negative way. (Mills; 98,99)

Metaphor

A metaphor is a figure of speech in which one word is implied to an item to which it is not actually appropriate. For example, man is a wolf; Sally is a block of ice. Both these metaphors refer to male and female sexuality. The 1st refers to a voluptuous man who hunts women in the same way as a wolf spires its prey, while the 2nd refers to a woman who is not interested in a man sexually. So, based on this stereotypical knowledge, we also analyze people's emotions in terms of heat and cool. Metaphor is used not only to create meaning but also to relive the thoughts of the speaker about a particular object (Mills, [1995](#), p. 105).

Jokes and Humour

A joke is an act of humor in which words are used in a special and clear-cut narrative framework to produce laughter. There are several jokes about women, and it depends on the audience's reaction. For example, a) Why did the women cross the road? B) that is a false question. What is she doing out of the kitchen.? Double intenders are also used to refer to women's sexuality. Mills stated that generally, humor comes under the male domain, so they create sexist jokes about women, which are hidden under humor. (Mills, [1995](#), p. 108)

Transitivity Choices

Halliday argues that transitivity is a set of options where the speaker consciously encodes his experience of external and internal worlds with the involvement of participants and their attendant circumstances. Transitivity choices are used to know about the role of human participants. Transitivity revolves around three sets of choices.

- 1) Material: Material is further divided into 2 types.
 - a. Material action intention
 - b. Material action supervention.
- 2) Mental: Mental is further divided into the mental internalized process and the mental externalize process.
- 3) Relational: For example, she raised her hand (Material), and she ended silently (mental). (Mills, [1995](#), p. 110-111)

Discourse Level

Character Rule

It is the rule that a character plays in a drama, novel, or short story, and so on. Character in a novel is not a simulacrum of human beings but a collection of signifiers set around a good name. The picture of clothing and facial significance is used to indicate the kind of judgment that the reader is supposing about the character. The representation of the male and female characters is different; females are portrayed in terms of their body parts like legs, faces, lips, and hips, while men are represented in their overall appearances like leather jackets, alfa Romeo, car, and Rolex watch. (Mills, [1995](#), p. 123,124)

Fragmentation

Fragmentation is the activity or condition of breaking or division of something into pieces and fragments. It is a technique in which the female body is portrayed in a fragmented form so the female appears as an item or stock of items for male looking. For example, her head, her eyes, her mouth, her neck. It is used to describe a female character while to describe a male character, only two anatomical are used: her eyes met his eyes and "his arm". Mills stated that fragmentation is used first to depersonalize and objectify the female body and secondly so that the female body does not appear as a unified being (Mills, [1995](#), p. 133,138).

Focalization

This term was introduced by French narrative theorist Gerard Genette. It refers to a viewpoint through which the narrative is delivered. It can also be defined as the demonstration of an act through the personal approach of a character. Focalization can be either external or internal. External focalization seems to be near to the narrating focalizer, and an example of a narrating focalizer is "A Passage to India," where the narrator is only inception of view, knowledge, and judgment about the character and events. External focalizers work in all times of narrative, present, past, and future, whereas internal focalizers work only in the present of a character. (Mills, [1995](#), p. 139,147)

Schemata

According to Rumelhart Schema, a data system is used to demonstrate the generic notions reserved in memory. Robert Hudge and Gunther Kress state that in order to understand discourse, there is more to it than simply the wording of the discourse. Schema depends upon the reader's already known information and experiences, and based on these experiences, we keep on interpreting the text. For example, the schema for going to a restaurant involves the first act of entering the restaurant, then being addressed by the waiter and demanding a table, and then ordering something to drink and eat, and it is the last, paying for food. (Mills, [1995](#), p. 150, 152)

Analysis

At Word Level

Generic Noun

By using generic nouns, Rumman Syed presents female experiences from male perspectives and takes males as a standard, or they have no alternatives. Mills ([1995](#)) defines that because of sexist language, all generic nouns portray the male experience of the world as the norm (Pg.66). It means generic nouns are nouns that are used for both males and Females, but in the English language it only gives the meaning of specific male gender like in most cases *-man* is used as a prefix or suffix such as manpower, policeman, postman which indicate that the reference is only given to male gender, there are several male-specific terms which were used to refers to female as well, but there was still ambiguity that woman is referred to in these terms or not. Mills stated that man is used as a prefix, such as a manhour, or an affix, such as seaman or fisherman because there is no generic alternative to such a noun. Generic nouns are not limited to 'man'; there are also some nouns and verbs that are used in the same way. Some words are specific for males but also refer to women as well. (67-69). Darwesh & Hussain ([2016](#)), in their article, find out that a generic noun in *The Handmaid's Tale* is used to indicate that male is the standard norm. Saima et al. ([2021](#)), in their article, find out that the Generic noun in *Domestic Crusaders* is used to show the female experience from a male perspective.

Awaiting Destiny

Chase those dreams everyone thought childish

Let them become the reality of a mature man (lines 9-10) (P, 17)

In the above lines, Rumman stereotypically uses generic nouns to make man the standard norm and also uses male experience for a female, like "mature man." This term is used for females by taking male experience and excluding females from this world. Here, Rumman advises females to pursue their infantile dreams and make those naive dreams a reality of a mature man. By using male-specific generic nouns, Rumman asserts that a woman's dream is foolish and imbecile. It has nothing to do with reality, but man is taken as standard, and everything man does is considered universal as Rumman says to the girl that she should take her dream to the position where it turns into the reality of a mature man.

Blended

"What matters is the part you act upon

To be a hero or to be a villain (Line 10-11) (P, 68)

In the above lines, Rumman uses the Generic specific noun of male for a female to declare that man is the standard. Rumman uses the generic noun "hero," which means a male character or protagonist in the movie or drama, while "villain," which means a negative character or antagonist in the movie. These terms are used for the female gender by picking the male experience of the world and eliminating her own experience. Here, the speaker says that loss and winning do not matter in life. What matters is the path you are choosing for yourself. Either you are choosing the path of villain, which is the quality of devil / Satan, or the path of hero, which is the quality of saint or conqueror for yourself it matters. The purpose of using the two generic specific nouns of male for the female is to declare man's superiority that only he has the supernatural quality of "hero" while woman can't. That's why the writer uses the man-associated term for females; there was no such specific heroic term for a female.

She is a Warrior

"She was born in the wrong era."

A warrior in the legend of her life" (Line 15-16) (P, 108)

In the above lines, Rumman uses generic specific nouns of male for female to show the superiority of male characteristics. Rumman uses the generic noun "worrier," which means "a strong, powerful, and unafraid person." This word is used for the female gender to experience the world from a male perspective because all those qualities associated with the word "worrier" came in the domain of masculinity. Rumman says that the girl in the tale of her life is a worrier who has opened her eyes to the wrong generation. By using the word worrier for her, Rumman portrays the female experience from a male perspective because the word warrior is a masculine term and mostly gives a masculine point of view.

A Survivor

'People called her agony; I corrected them

"She was a fighter. She was a survivor

With broken exterior and shattered interior' (lines 6,7,8) (P, 108)

In the above lines, Rumman uses generic specific nouns of male for female to show male universality and female deviated position. Rumman uses the word "fighter:" which means a person who does not accept failure and fights till the last breath and also uses the word "survivor," which means a person who survives in a difficult situation in which other people lost their lives. These two terms are used for females to train them like the male gender. Here the male is taken as a standard because the words "Fighter" and "Survivor" are masculine terms in which fighter is associated with a soldier and survivor is associated with a warrior who came alive from the battlefield. Rumman says that humankind named this girl as misery; I told them that she was not agony but a fighter and survivor of her life because it was visible from her fractured frame and fragmented interior. The purpose of using the words fighter and survivor for females is to show that males commit behavior as generic or normal while that of a female is deviated. Here, the female quality of fighting and surviving is portrayed from a male point of view.

Women as a Marked Form

Rumman Syed uses the element of feminist stylistic marked form for women, which shows that women are fragile, dependent, and subordinated creatures and shows the lack of seriousness. Mills ([1995](#)) states that females (women) are always seen as marked while males (men) are unmarked. This means that men's work is always considered to be standard while women's work is considered to be derivation from the so-called norms. (Pg.7). Darwesh and Hussain, ([2016](#)). Their article stated that lexically marked terms used for females not only represent frivolity and suppression but also represent their lower position in society.

Saif-UI-Maluk

*"It's the Princess of Aqua,
waiting anxiously to be admired"* (lines 15, 16) (P, 20)

In these lines, Rumman uses the marked form "*Princess*" for a woman. "*Princess*" refers to someone who enjoys a luxurious and comfortable life in someone else position; other people take care of her, and she always waits for other people's praise. Rumman adds the suffix -ess to the base form *prince* to make women the marked form. In the above lines, Rumman asserts that the *Princess* is a subordinated and dependent woman who lacks self-confidence. The speaker says that the *Princess* is so dependent on other people that she worriedly waits for other people to adore her.

She is a Warrior

"She was enchantress of imperfection" (lines 9) (P, 108)

In these lines, Rumman uses the marked form *enchantress* for women, which refers to a sorceress who keeps people under her spell/charm. The word *enchanter* means a person who also does magic, but Rumman adds the suffix -ess to the base form of *enchanter* to show the negative stance/posture of women. In these lines, Rumman asserts that she was an (*enchantress/magician / sorcerous*) who sexually / physically attracted people toward herself. But apart from this, she was full of faults and weaknesses, calling her an *enchantress* of imperfection, which shows the negative and dependent position of women.

Imperfect Perfection

"A priestess her divine power reduces many to their knee" (Lines 12) (P, 153)

In these lines, Rumman uses the marked form *Priestess* for Female, which refers to a divine and mysterious woman. The word "*Priest*" means a person who holds religious authority, but Rumman adds the suffix -ess to the base form "*Priest*" to show the adverse position of women who diminish people down through their mysterious power. By using the word *Priestess* for woman, Rumman reveals the negative status of woman, which is her mysterious nature, as in the next line that it will take millions of years to apprehend/understand her mysterious nature. "*A Poetess who bleed both fairytales and nightmares"* (Lines 14). Rumman also uses the marked form *Poetess* for Female, which refers to a woman who is a poet. The word *poet* means a person who is gifted with imaginative thought and feeling, but Rumman added the suffix -ess to the base form of the poet to show the subordinate and lower intellectual level of a woman. Along with the marked form, Ruman uses the negative word "*Bleed*," which means to give strong emphasis on something or to reveal the hidden thing. Here, Rumman shows the unreal nature of the *Poetess* (woman) whose only emphasis is on the imaginative story of a happy ending and also on the terrific feelings associated with a bad night dream. These lines show the low intellectual level of female "*Poets*" who, unlike males, do not describe the realistic portrayal of nature/society but only focus on fairy tales and nightmares.

Divine Love

"Hold her firm and caress her as if she is a Goddess" (Line 1) (P, 160)

In these lines, Rumman uses the marked form *Goddess* for woman which refers to a female deity who is praised for her physical charm. The word "god" means supreme power who controls the whole universe, but Rumman adds the suffix -ess to the base form "god," which shows the fragile and dependent position of women in society as she gives a clear indication in the subtitle that she was always protected by him, it means she depends on him. By using the word *Goddesses* for female, Ruman exhibits her fragile nature as she says that you should take care of her due to her alluring and delicate nature and also hold her tightly so that she may not fall.

Endearments and Diminutives

Ruman uses Endearments and Diminutives words for women, which reflects her subordinated and lower position in stereotypical society. Mills stated that diminutives can be used to show affection, but they can also be used to humiliate someone; males use this term to maintain hierarchical relationships. Mills (1995) stated that there are certain terms that males use specifically for their fellow female companions, such as baby, doll, flower petal, etc. (Pg.89). it means that certain diminutive words are mostly used by males for females, which refers to their delicate and sexual behavior and also to keep their hierarchal linkage. Females can also use such diminutives but in a specific context and relation.

Trust Me Papa

"Your little girl is all grown up,"

"Let me fight my battle on my own" (lines 7-8) (P, 14)

In these lines, Rumman uses the diminutive word "little girl" to show the female's dependent position. Girl refers to any teenage girl who is not yet married. Here, Ruman reveals that the girl's father makes her dependent on others by not giving her the freedom to go outside or the freedom to demolish everything that comes her way to achieve her goals. These lines show that the girl's father did not give her freedom only because they considered her an immature little girl who was not yet married. After all, they only associate maturity with marriage.

Curiosity did Kill the Cat

"Curiosity did kill the cat" (Line 12) (P, 81)

In this line, Rumman uses the endearment "Cat" to refer to women. A cat is a four-legged, delicate, and domestic animal with fur. By using the word cat for woman, Rumman associates her with a cute small animal. Along with the diminutives, Rumman uses the negative word "curiosity," which is the quality of a cat, like a cat was always in search of something, and that quest search put her in trouble. By using this proverb, Rumman reveals the curious nature of a woman who was in search of love experimentation, but that inquisitive search for love entrapped her in the cage because the male person was not truly in love with her, and he was only exploiting her body.

Heart Verses mind

"Shh baby girl! Bite on your hand; don't be so. Loud" (P, 116)

In this line, Rumman uses the diminutive words "Baby girl" for female which shows her smallness, and lower position. The word baby means a small child who was not yet able to walk or talk. Here Rumman reveals the cruel nature of society that how they were silencing females as she says to the baby girl that you should not scream loudly otherwise someone will listen to your voice and your life will be ruined.

Practice Run

"It's a practice Run baby" (Line 6) (P, 124)

In these lines, Rumman uses the diminutive word baby for female which refers to a small child who was unable to walk or talk. By using the word "Baby" for female Rumman shows her immaturity as she says to the girl that it is a practice run for you baby because you are not yet that much mature to decide anything for yourself or to soothe yourself.

At Sentence level

Metaphor

At the sentence level, metaphor is used by Umme Rumman Syed in her anthology "Beautiful Inadequacies" to show the cruel, lustful, and barbaric nature of the male gender. Mills (1995) defines metaphor as an indirect comparison

of two items that are not literarily true. (pg.105). This means that the writer compares two items that belong to a different domain to create meaning from them. Such as sexuality as described on the basis of heat and lack of heat. So, sexuality and heat are two different items, but in order to create meaning, the writer compares them with each other. Mills stated that metaphor is used not only to create meaning but also to relive the thoughts of the speaker about a particular object. (105). Siregar et al. (2020), in their article, find that the metaphor which is used for men in "Home Body" portrays them in a negative way who always exploit the women's bodies.

Resilience

"They are sucking my blood

As if they are vampires (lines 1-2) (P, 27)

The above lines of Rumman's poetry reflect that women are treated crudely by males like vampires who are ingesting blood from the female body to satisfy their thirst. According to Jean Marigny, a vampire is the unrestful creature of the darkness that came as a result of the bovine plague in Serbia (ROTV. pg.8). It is believed that these creatures came out of the grave at night and attacked loved ones. By using the word vampire for man, Rumman actually associates him with a Zombie who always feeds on living creatures, just like the man in the above lines is living on the vital fluid of that woman from whom he drinks blood. She uses the plural pronoun "they" for man, which means that it was not a single vampire but there are a group of vampires who brutally torture her as she says, "Hurt me Inexorably" (Line 3), but she tolerates the suffering without showing any sorrow or resentment. By doing this, she wanted to justify her power of endurance and to examine her bravery and stableness as she gives a clear indication in the subtitle that her body skin is as strong as the vampire's spiny teeth. She further says that no matter how much they try to break me, I will bear it to my last breath to show them my strength (Wood, 2009).

Hypocrite

"My killer is the one pretending to be the victim" (Line 6)(P, 45)

Rumman also uses the metaphor of killer for males, which means any person who causes the death of a living person. Rumman asserts that women are always the victim of men's cruel behavior as the man leads women to death by the cruel act of killing. Rumman also reveals the other side of man by using the word hypocrite for him, which means a person who pretends to be someone else to hide his real face. By this, Rumman asserts that man is not only the doer of a victim but is a hypocrite also because after killing her, he came to her funeral with the flower in his hand in order to hide his dirty hand, which was stained with her blood "As if they can hide the hands splashed with red" (Pg.45, line 5). She further stated that above all this, my killer is so fake that despite accepting his crime of killing me, he disguises himself as an innocent person.

Men consider themselves superior and independent, and they suppress their women in different ways. Mills (1995) defines metaphor as the major component that not only represents the meaning of the word but also reveals the thoughts of the speaker (Pg. 105). It means that metaphor not only produces the meaning of the literary text but can also expose the idea of the writer, poet, or speaker about a particular thing. Kanwal (2022), in her article, stated that the metaphor used for the male in *Beyond the Fields* reflects the strong, cruel, and violent, while the metaphor used for the female portrayed her as passive to male behavior.

She Drowned

He was the devil in an angel disguise (line 9) (P, 55)

Rumman uses the metaphor of the devil for male, which means a brutal, vicious, and inhuman person who always deceives a woman to mislead her path. Men consider women inferior in the sense that they have power, and they exercise that power over women/ while, in order to hide their devil faces, they disguise themselves as an innocent

person. Woman, on the other hand, was always an obedient creature who bore every harsh treatment silently, and males took advantage of her soundless behavior. In other lines, Rumman called a predator to males due to their cruel behavior towards females. They dealt women as a predator and their prey with enmity. "He was smirking at his latest prey" (pg.55, line 7). These lines suggest that males harassed women in the same way as the predator was haunting his prey. The pronoun "You" suggests that the predator is a male who was sneering at his latest prey, and his latest prey was a female who was fractured by an atrocious predator.

Victim of Brutality

There are burns on my heart

The beast has mutilated me (Line 3-4) (P, 94)

In these lines, Rumman uses the metaphor of beast for male, which means an evil, rapacious creature who harassed her. Rumman exposes the cruel reality of a society where women are always the victims of adultery as she states in the line (Line 1-7), there are scars on my skin, and the erroneous finger touched me. Rumman also uses the word assaulters for male, which means a person who attacked or raped. By this, she asserts males are independent in society while Females are dependent and subordinated because while sexually abusing a girl, the male is wandering free, but the only act of ignominy is related to the female. No matter how much she tries to clean the stain, she will remain suspicious. She further says that both man and society are responsible for my damaged skin because society never hears my voice; they always silenced me from exposing the reality. "But humanity never heard my plea." Rumman also uses the metaphor of rapist for male, which means a person who by force sexually abuses someone. Rumman stated that a woman is always sexually harassed by a man, so she wanted to kill him by putting her hand on his throat to receive the justice that she always deserved.

Rumman stated that apart from suppression, females are still struggling to raise their voices for their fellow creatures. Mills (1995) stated that metaphor is the major component that not only represents the meaning of the world but also reveals the thought of the speaker (Pg.115). It means when the writer uses a metaphor for someone on one level. This metaphor gives meaning on the other level. It also reveals the thoughts of the speaker.

I Apologize, Little One

They are heinous, wretched creatures of hell. (Line 6) (P, 179)

Rumman uses the metaphor of heinous wretched creature for male, which means an atrocious evil person who killed the little girl by the cruel act of rape. "And the brutalist kept on rapping you apart and feeding on your chaste self" (Pg.180, line 13). Rumman also uses the word brutalist for male, which means a ferocious person who satisfies his thirst for sexually harassing the little girl. "The inhuman and atrocious will suffer a thousand times over" (Pg. 181, Line 27). Furthermore, Rumman also uses the metaphor of inhuman and atrocious for males who always mutilated the little girl with their heinous fingers. Here, male sexuality is compared to animal behavior in that the male hunts the little girl in the same way as the bigger animals tear the smaller animals. In the last line, the speaker raises a voice for her fellow little creature as she states, I will not die until this evil is not clear from the world.

At Discourse Level

Fragmentation

Rumman describes female characters through their different body parts, which reflects that she is merely physical objects or entities for a male glance. Mills (1995) defines fragmentation as a method of representing Females through their different body parts (Pg.133). This means that in the literature, females are shown in terms of their anatomical parts, while males are shown in their overall appearance. This leads to gender discrimination. Fragmentation is used first to depersonalize and objectify the female body and, secondly, so that the female body

does not appear as a unified being. (133). Darwesh & Hussain (2016), in their article, stated that the representation of women in fragmented form reduces the woman's identity to a mere object, which means that a woman is not considered a human being but just a physical object.

Beautiful Imperfections

*"Protruded teeth and thin lips
Dull eyes and dumpy hair
Freckled cheeks and elongated ear
Chubby waist and distorted step (p. 92)*

In the above lines, Rumman describes the female through her different body parts, which display her defective body. Apart from fragmentation, Rumman uses the negative term for female body parts. She has thin lips, obstructive teeth, tedious eyes, short and curly hair, spotted cheeks, and an overweight waist. Along with the imperfect structure, she has a deformity in her walking style, which means that she is a disabled person. Here, Rumman does a negative representation of the female body, from her lips to her deformed walking style, to show the adverse position of women. By doing this fragmented representation of women, Rumman shows the biased nature of society and how they are rejecting women on the basis of their less attractive features because the speaker herself says that all these imperfections are enough for my disapproval. The purpose of this fragmented representation is to show that a female is not a whole being but rather a mixture of deformed features. Despite society's unjust attitude towards females, the speaker is brave enough to accept her body with all its deformity, as she says in the last line, "Yet I am Beautifully Imperfect," which shows that the speaker has no problem with her deformed body. She is happy with how she is.

Soldier Bride

*"Red gown, ruby lips, and that blush on cheeks
Hena on her hands with his name in the middle
Bright and sparkling eyes that were So eager
He promised he would come to take her
Riding in a jeep, her knight-in-combat boots
He entered in green and white and looked so magnificent. (Line 5-6) (p. 110)*

In the above lines, Rumman portrays the female through her body parts, while the male is described in his overall appearance and profession, which causes gender discrimination on the basis of representation. By doing a fragmented representation of the female, she wears a red gown, red lipstick on her lips, and a glow on her cheek. She writes his name with Hena on her palm. It reflects that she is just a sexual object who is decorating herself for him. Rumman also shows the dependent and subordinate position of a woman by describing the female actions that she waits for him with shining eyes and anxious ears. On the other hand, Rumman also represents the male gender as independent and is described through his overall appearance, as he wore a green and white shirt with combat boots and rode in a jeep. It shows his profession as a soldier. This biased representation of each gender reflects that woman's role is only to do marriage and decorate herself for the male gaze while that of a male is independent of going outside, doing a job, etc.

Eating Disorder Are Funny

*People ask me to take care of myself
Of my body, my exterior
My stomach begs me at 3:00 in the morning to stop squeezing it
My throat parches, my teeth torn yellow, my vocal cord stop
Cooperating, and my two digits go deeper among them to extract something, anything (p. 145)*

In these lines, Rumman states that the female body consists of two parts: exterior (which is the outer physical shape) and interior (which is the internal body system). Rumman declares that society only gives preference to the exterior ("Physical Beauty") of the female body as she says that people told me to take care of your exterior like teeth, face, and eyes because her teeth turn yellow, her eyes go deeper, her throat becomes dries because of not eating properly in order to keep her exterior fit and slim. Rumman says that in spite of the exterior, the interior is more essential to be taken care of; like she says, my stomach asks me at 3:00 am not to press it because it was empty. So, she was in favor of eating in order to fulfill the need for an interior body. In the last line, Rumman gives a direct response to the people that my body is not a joke for your entertainment; I am happy in the way I am: "My body is not your entertainment house" (line 19).

Conclusion

The present study concluded that woman was always suppressed and subjugated by men through different methods. This study presents different feminist stylistic elements that are portrayed by Umm e Rumman Syed in her anthology *Beautiful Inadequacies* (Aug 2020). This thesis has been analyzed by using textual analysis as a methodological framework. This study adopted a feminist stylistic model of Sara Mills (1995) at word, phrase /sentence, and discourse level. The number of elements used for this study is generic nouns, women as the marked form, endearments and diminutives at a word level, metaphor, transitivity choice and presupposition and inferences at phrase /sentence level, and fragmentation at discourse level. Rumman's anthology (2020) explores the main problem related to women in stereotypical societies, like rape, physical abuse, lack of freedom, suppression, and rejection. This research also includes that, to some extent, women were struggling for themselves. In the present study, Rumman constructs a female persona for herself to share the problem of every woman in a more general way. Rumman poetry mainly reflects the harsh reality of the society in which she lives, where women are treated in an ill manner. At the word level, generic nouns in *Beautiful Inadequacies* like mature man, hero, warrior, and survivor reflect that man is the standard of the norm while that of a woman is marginal because these nouns are Generic, but it presents women /female experiences from a male perspective. By using marked forms like Princess, Enchantresses, goddesses, and priestesses, women are shown as subordinated creatures who are dependent on men.

The princess is a girl who enjoys the unearned wealth of the king. Through diminutives, a word like a little girl, cat, baby girl, and baby woman was assigned a lower position to suppress them so that they may not revolt. At the phrase/sentence level, metaphors in anthologies like vampires, killers, devils, and beasts reflect the men's cruel behavior towards women as they suck women's blood, kill them, rape them, and mutilate women's body. By using presupposition and inferences, it is shown that the woman was struggling to get the freedom and independence that the man has, but they don't. Men have the freedom of choice of marriage, but women do not. Rumman also gives hope to all the rejected and dejected souls that they should not be worried; they are beautiful in their own way. By using transitivity choices, the study maintains that man was an active actor in all the action because he was involved in all the material processes, while women are present as passive recipients of male behavior. The women are either engaged in relational or mental processes. At the discourse level, fragmentation is used to portray women not as a whole being but rather as a mixture of imperfect fragments based on which she always faces rejection and deprivation from society. The study maintains that men always try to oppress women as they consider themselves powerful creatures and they exercise their power over women because women are considered obedient, silent, and passive. The overall theme of the present study is love, nature, betrayal, racism, traditional and familial values, inequality, and injustice in the cruel society in which the Poetess lives.

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